

DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITĀTE
DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITY

DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITĀTES ZINĀTŅU DAĻA
SCIENCE DEPARTMENT OF DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITY

DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITĀTES JAUNO ZINĀTNIEKU ASOCIĀCIJA
DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITY ASSOCIATION OF YOUNG RESEARCHERS

**DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITĀTES
60. STARPTAUTISKĀS ZINĀTNISKĀS
KONFERENCES RAKSTU KRĀJUMS**

**PROCEEDINGS OF THE 60th
INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
OF DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITY**

C. DAĻA. HUMANITĀRĀS ZINĀTNES

PART C. HUMANITIES

DAUGAVPILS UNIVERSITĀTE
AKADĒMISKAIS APGĀDS „SAULE”
2018

Apstiprināts Daugavpils Universitātes Zinātnes padomes sēdē 2019. gada 16. janvārī, protokols Nr. 1. /
Approved in the meeting of Daugavpils University Science Council on January 16, 2019; minutes No 1.

Kokina I., red. *Daugavpils Universitātes 60. starptautiskās zinātniskās konferences rakstu krājums. C. daļa "Humanitārās zinātnes" = Proceedings of the 60th International Scientific Conference of Daugavpils University. Part C "Humanities"*. Daugavpils: Daugavpils Universitāte, 2018.

***Daugavpils Universitātes 60. starptautiskās zinātniskās konferences
Programmas komiteja / Programme Committee of
the 60th International Scientific Conference of Daugavpils University***

Dr. biol., prof. Arvīds Barševskis (Daugavpils University, Latvia, Chairman of Scientific Committee)
Dr. philol., prof. Maija Burima (Daugavpils University, Latvia, Vice Chairman)
Dr. biol., prof. Ingrīda Šauliene (Siauliai University, Lithuania)
Dr., assist. prof. Detlev Lindau-Bank (University of Vechta, Germany)
PhD, asoc. prof. Enne Koresaare (University of Tartu, Estonia)
PhD, prof. Yesudas Choondassery (Berkeley College, ASV)
Dr. hum., prof. Genovaitė Kačiuškienė (Siauliai University, Lithuania)
Dr. habil. philol., prof. Ina Druviete (University of Latvia)
Dr. hab., prof. nadzw. Jakub Bartoszewski (State University of Applied Sciences in Konin, Poland)
PhD, prof. Ulla Harkonen (Joensuu University, Finland)
Dr. paed., prof. Małgorzata Suswillo (University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, Poland)
Dr. habil. sc. ing., prof. Sławomir Partycki (The John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin, Poland)
Dr. oec., prof. Alena Vankevich (Vitebsk State University of Technology, Belarus)
PhD, prof. Geoffrey R. Swain (University of Glasgow, United Kingdom)
Dr. habil. biol., prof. Yarosław Skłodowski (Warsaw University of Life Sciences, Poland)
Dr. habil. art., prof. Romualdas Apanavičius (Vytautas Magnus University, Lithuania)
Dr. habil. art., prof. Ludmila Kazantseva (Astrakhan Conservatory and Volgograd Institute of Art and Culture, Russia)
Dr. habil. oec. Manuela Tvaronavičiene (The General Jonas Žemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania, Lithuania)
Dr. habil. sc. soc., prof. Antanas Makštutis (The General Jonas Žemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania, Lithuania)
Dr. habil. philol., prof. emeritus Fjodors Fjodorovs (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. philol., prof. Vilma Šaudiņa (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. habil. philol., prof. Zaiga Ikere (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. hist., prof. Aleksandrs Ivanovs (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. hist., prof. Irēna Saleniece (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. paed., prof. Elfrīda Krastiņa (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. habil. paed., Dr. habil. psych., prof. Aleksejs Vorobjovs (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. sc. soc., prof. Vladimirs Meņšikovs (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. phys., prof. Valfrīds Paškevičs (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. biol., prof. Artūrs Škute (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. biol., prof. Inese Kokina (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. phys., prof. Edmunds Tamanis (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. art., prof. Ēvalds Daugulis (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. iur., prof. Vitolds Zahars (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
PhD, prof. Dzintra Iliško (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. theol. prof. Anita Stašulāne (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. psych., prof. Irēna Kokina (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. paed., prof. Jeļena Davidova (Daugavpils University, Latvia)
Dr. paed., asoc. prof. Edgars Znutiņš (Daugavpils University, Latvia)

***Daugavpils Universitātes 60. starptautiskās zinātniskās konferences
Rīcības komiteja / Organizing Committee of
the 60th International Scientific Conference of Daugavpils University***

Maija Burima (Chairperson of Organizing Committee)
Eva Kasprenoka (Vice Chairman)
Zeltīte Barševska, Žans Badins, Juris Soms, Uldis Valainis, Kristīna Aksjuta, Diāna Ozola, Kristīne Bule, Valērijs Dombrovskis, Ilze Meldere, Zaiga Lāce, Miervaldis Mendriks, Laura Vilcāne

*Daugavpils Universitātes 60. starptautiskās zinātniskās konferences
rakstu krājuma redaklēģija / Editorial staff of
the 60th International Scientific Conference of Daugavpils University*

Dr. psych., prof. Irēna Kokina – redaktore / editor

Dr. oec, doc. Ludmila Aleksejeva

Dr. biol., doc. Līga Antoņeviča

Dr. art., Mg. paed., doc., pētn. Zeltīte Barševska

Dr. biol., prof. Arvīds Barševskis

Mg. biol., lekt. Jeļena Buiko

Dr. philol., prof. Maija Burima

Dr. oec, doc. Aina Čaplinska

Dr. paed., prof. Jeļena Davidova

Dr. psych., asoc. prof. Valērijs Dombrovskis

PhD, pētn. Ilona Fjodorova

PhD, prof. Dzintra Iliško

Dr. hist, prof. Aleksandrs Ivanovs

Dr. chem., doc. Jeļena Kirilova

Dr. biol., prof. Inese Kokina

Dr. paed., pētn. Mārīte Kravale-Pauliņa

Dr. iur., doc. Anatolijs Kriviņš

Dr. philol., doc. Ingrīda Kupšāne

Mg. art., Mg. paed., lekt. Ilze Meldere

Dr. phys., prof. Valfrīds Paškevičs

Dr. iur. doc. Jānis Radionovs

Dr. hist, prof. Irēna Saleniece

Dr. paed., pētn. Astrīda Skrinda

Mg. vid. plān., lekt. Anastasija Smoļakova

Dr. hist, asoc. prof. Henrihs Soms

Dr. geol., asoc. prof. Juris Soms

Dr. iur., prof. Vitolds Zahars

Dr. paed., pētn. Gaļina Zavadska

Atbildīgās par izdevumu / Responsible for the Edition

Olita Miglāne (olita.miglane@du.lv)

Anna Vanaga (anna.vanaga@du.lv)

Daugavpils Universitātē docētāju un studējošo zinātniskās konferences notiek kopš 1958. gada. Konferencēm ir starpdisciplinārs raksturs un tajās piedalās gan studējošie, gan docētāji, gan arī ievērojami zinātnieki no dažādām pasaules valstīm. Daugavpils Universitātes 60. starptautiskās zinātniskās konferences pētījumu tematika bija ļoti plaša – eksaktās, humanitārās, izglītības, mākslas un sociālo zinātņu jomās.

Zinātnisko rakstu krājumā *Daugavpils Universitātes 60. starptautiskās zinātniskās konferences rakstu krājums = Proceedings of the 60th International Scientific Conference of Daugavpils University* apkopoti 2018. gada 26.–27. aprīlī konferencē prezentētie materiāli.

Daugavpils Universitātes 60. starptautiskās zinātniskās konferences rakstu krājums tiek publicēts 3 daļās: A. daļa. *Dabaszinātnes*; B. daļa. *Sociālās zinātnes*; C. daļa. *Humanitārās zinātnes*.

The annual scientific conferences at Daugavpils University have been organized since 1958. The themes of research presented at the conferences cover all spheres of life. Due to the facts that the conference was of interdisciplinary character and that its participants were students and outstanding scientists from different countries, the subjects of scientific investigations were very varied – in the domains of exact sciences, the humanities, education, art and social sciences.

The results of scientific investigations presented during the conference are collected in the collection of scientific articles *Proceedings of the 60th International Scientific Conference of Daugavpils University*.

Proceedings of the 60th International Scientific Conference of Daugavpils University are published in three parts: part A. *Natural sciences*; part B. *Social Sciences*; part C. *Humanities*.

SATURS / CONTENTS

VALODNIECĪBA, LITERATŪRZINĀTNE / LINGUISTICS, LITERARY STUDIES

<i>Oksana Kovzele</i>	SVĒTKU UZTVERES MAIŅAS FIKSĀCIJA LATGALIEŠU DZEJĀ	6
<i>Sarmīte Buholce</i>	LATGALES IDENTITĀTES MEKLĒJUMI Ā. ERSĀ DARBOS	17
<i>Diāna Ozola</i>	LATVIEŠU IDENTITĀTES UN ASIMILĀCIJAS TĒLOJUMS I. LEIŠA UN U. BRIEŽA CEĻOJUMU DIENASGRĀMATĀ „LATVIEŠUS SIBĪRIJĀ MEKLĒJOT”	24
<i>Inta Genese-Plaude</i>	POPULĀRĀ KULTŪRA AUGUSTA DEGLAVA ROMĀNA „RĪGA” 1. DAĻĀ	33

VĒSTURE / HISTORY, HISTORY OF CULTURE

<i>Ieva Pīgozne</i>	REUSE OF GARMENTS AND ACCESSORIES OF LATGALIAN CLOTHING IN THE 19 TH CENTURY	40
<i>Aiga Bērziņa</i>	PRISONS IN LATGALE DURING THE INITIAL PERIOD OF ACTIVITIES OF THE MAIN BOARD OF PRISONS, 1920–1921	49

MĀKSLA / ART

<i>Sandra Maskaļova, Zeltīte Barševska</i>	ANALYSIS OF CHARACTERISTICS OF CROSS-BORDER CULTURAL PROJECTS	60
<i>Sandra Lukjanova- Zarjanova</i>	CONCEPTUAL ART PHENOMENA OF THE PAST PERIOD	68
<i>Valērija Černova</i>	CONTEMPORARY ART FEATURES IN LATVIA IN 2016–2018	78
<i>Žanna Vērdiņa</i>	CONTEMPORARY TRENDS OF MIXED MEDIA PAINTING TECHNIQUE IN LATVIA AND IN THE WORLD	90
<i>Santa Riževska</i>	AESTHETIC POSITIONS IN PAINTING IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERN ART IN LATVIA AND WORLD-WIDE	100
<i>Darina Kroitore</i>	DESIGN AND ART – COMMON AND DISTINCTIVE	111
<i>Viktorija Loktionova, Aina Strode</i>	GAME DESIGN AS AN ADVERTISING TOOL	122
<i>Silvija Ozola</i>	THE INFLUENCE OF BYZANTIUM FORTIFIED URBAN STRUCTURES BUILDING TRADITIONS ON FORMATION OF GERMAN ADMINISTRATIVE CENTERS IN LIVONIAN ORTHODOX LANDS AND IN PRUSSIA IN THE 13 TH CENTURY	134
<i>Silvija Ozola</i>	TOWER HOUSE – STRATEGICALLY SIGNIFICANT COMPONENT OF POWER CENTRES’ FORTIFIED BUILDING COMPLEXES IN LIVONIA AND THE TEUTONIC ORDER STATE DURING 13 TH –14 TH CENTURIES	166
<i>Līga Strode, Aina Strode</i>	POSSIBILITIES OF PROVIDING SUSTAINABLE DESIGN IN RECREATION ZONES IN FLOODING AREAS OF RIVERS	199
<i>Santa Miežīte, Diāna Apele</i>	VISUAL ANALYSIS OF VIĻAKA MUNICIPLITY MUSEUM WITHIN CONTEXT OF DIGITAL CULTURE	209
<i>Normunds Kozlovs, Ilva Skulte</i>	COUNTERCULTURE SIGNS IN URBAN SPACE: GRAFFITI	219

VĒSTURE / HISTORY, HISTORY OF CULTURE

REUSE OF GARMENTS AND ACCESSORIES OF LATGALIAN CLOTHING IN THE 19TH CENTURY

Ieva Pīgozne

Institute of Latvian History at the University of Latvia, Kalpaka bulvaris 4, Rīga LV-1050,
pigozne@inbox.lv

Abstract

Reuse of Garments and Accessories of Latgalian Clothing in the 19th Century

Key Words: reuse, clothing, Latgale, Latvia, 19th century

The paper discusses reuse and second use of pieces of clothing and accessories worn by the Latvian-speaking peasants living in Daugavpils, Ludza, and Rēzekne districts of the Governorate of Vitebsk in the 19th century.

Traditional clothing reflects the local traditions of producing, ornamenting and wearing clothing and it was worn by local Latvian peasants till the second half of the 19th century. Latgalian traditional clothing has not been researched to the same extent as that of the other regions.

This paper studies how items of traditional clothing in Latgale were reused and therefore were not collected by museums, as well as what effect this had on the formation of the museum collections and what has to be considered when researching traditional Latgalian dress. It analyses evidence of reused garments and repurposed accessories when they were outworn or out of fashion. It is based on a thorough examination of the interviews carried out by the ethnographers of the Monument Board in 1925, 1926, 1937, and 1943, drawings, photographs and garments stored at the National History Museum of Latvia, Archives of Latvian Folklore, as well as interviews carried out by Ieva Pigozne in 2017. This paper reveals one part of the results of the postdoctoral research project "Development of Folk Dress in Latgale in the 19th Century" funded by The European Regional Development Fund.

This paper concludes that Latgalian peasant's festive clothing was usually worn as everyday clothing when it was worn out; many garments were reused as leg wraps or nappies for babies. Footwear was worn as long as possible or kept for funerary attire. Thus there was rarely anything left to be collected by the museums in the first half of the 20th century. Such popular accessories as woollen sashes were usually repurposed and were used as decorative gift wraps, for lowering a coffin into the grave during the funeral, tying babies or as upper parts of slippers. Sashes were still made and kept in many homes till the World War II but they were not used for holding the ladies' skirts as in the first half of the 19th century. Abundance of sashes contributed to creation of a misconception that they were used together with traditional clothing and thus to unfounded formation of sets of Latgalian traditional clothing.

Kopsavilkums

Apģērba un tā piederumu atkārtota izmantošana Latgalē 19. gadsimtā

Atslēgvārdi: Atkārtota izmantošana, apģērbs, Latgale, Latvija, 19. gadsimts

Pētījumā analizēts, kā latgaliešu zemnieki, kuri 19. gadsimtā dzīvoja Vitebskas guberņas Daugavpils, Rēzeknes un Ludzas apriņķos, atkārtoti un otrreizēji izmantoja novalkātās tradicionālā apģērba daļas.

Tradicionālais apģērbs atspoguļo vietējās apģērba izgatavošanas, rotāšanas un valkāšanas tradīcijas. Latviešu zemnieki to valkāja līdz 19. gadsimta otrajai pusei. Latgales tradicionālais apģērbs līdz šim ir pētīts mazāk nekā citu novadu tērpi. Pētījums atklāj, kā tradicionālā apģērba daļas Latgalē tika pilnībā izlietotas un nesaglabājās līdz brīdim, kad tās varēja tikt savāktas muzeju kolekcijām, tādā veidā ietekmējot to veidošanos. Šos procesus jāņem vērā tradicionālā Latgales apģērba pētniecībā. Rakstā uzrādītas liecības tam, kā novalkātie vai no modes izgājušie apģērba gabali tika otrreizēji izmantoti, bet aksesuāri tika lietoti citiem mērķiem. Pētījums balstīts rūpīgā avotu analizē: 1925., 1926., 1937. un 1943. gadā veiktajās Pieminekļu valdes etnogrāfisko ekspedīciju intervijās, Latvijas Nacionālajā Vēstures muzejā glabātajās fotogrāfijās un apģērba daļās, Latviešu folkloras krātuves Paražu kartotēkā, kā arī Ievas Pigoznes 2017. gadā veiktajās intervijās Latgalē. Rakstā atspoguļota daļa no Eiropas Reģionālā Attīstības fonda finansētā pēcdoktorantūras projekta „Apģērba attīstība Latgalē 19. gadsimtā” pētījuma rezultātiem.

Pētījumā secināts, ka Latgales zemnieku goda tērpa daļas pēc to apvalkāšanas parasti tika valkātas kā ikdienas un darba apģērbs. Daudzu apģērba gabalu audums tika otrreizēji izmantots kājautiem vai bērnu autiņiem. Apavi tika valkāti tik ilgi, cik vien iespējams vai glabāti bērnu apģērbam. Tādējādi līdz 20. gadsimta sākumam, kad tika veidotas muzeju kolekcijas, saglabājušos priekšmetu bija ļoti maz. Savukārt tādi populāri aksesuāri kā austās jostas arvien tika izmantotas, taču citiem mērķiem – kāzu dāvanu apsīšanai, zārka ielaišanai kapā, zīdaiņu autiņu apsīšanai vai koka klikatu virsējo daļu izgatavošanai. Austo jostu izmantošana daudzās mājās turpinājās līdz Otrajam Pasaules karam, taču tās netika izmantotas sieviešu brunču saturēšanai kā 19. gadsimta pirmajā pusē. Pieejamo jostu lielais skaits ietekmēja aplama priekšstata izveidošanos, saskaņā ar kuru tās tika nepamatoti pievienotas sakomplektētajiem Latgales tradicionālajiem tērpiem.

Introduction

The paper discusses reuse, second use and repurposing of pieces of traditional clothing and accessories worn by the Latvian-speaking peasants living in Daugavpils, Ludza, and Rēzekne districts of the Governorate of Vitebsk in the 19th century. The aim of the article is to analyse the evidence of reuse, examine what the reused pieces were used for and show how this influenced the formation of the museum collections.

Traditional clothing reflects the local traditions of producing, ornamenting and wearing clothing and it was worn by local Latvian peasants till the second half of the 19th century. Traditional clothing for women consisted of a long linen shirt, woollen or linen skirt, an apron, a jacket, a shawl for festive occasions, a coat, leg-wraps or socks, footwear, one or two head coverings. Traditional clothing for men consisted of a linen shirt, linen or woollen trousers, a jacket, one or two coats, leg-wraps or socks, footwear, a hat.

Latgalian traditional clothing has not been researched to the same extent as that of the other regions. Among the very few studies devoted to the Latgalian clothing of the 19th century, earlier research does not mention reuse of garments (Slava 1973), and the more recent one touches upon this subject in one sentence (Bremze, Rozenberga, Ziņģīte 2003: 186). Reuse of traditional Latvian garments has never been the topic of any research, and also studies devoted to other regions pay little attention to this problem, mentioning that the fabric of skirts or shawls were used as lining, underwear or children's clothing (Bremze, Rozenberga, Ziņģīte 1997: 11; Jansone 2016: 90).

Data for this study were obtained from thorough examination of the interviews carried out and drawings and photographs made by the ethnographers of the Monument Board in 1925, 1926, 1937 and 1943, as well as the garments stored at the National History Museum of Latvia, interviews carried out by Ieva Pigozne in 2017, and published sources. All this material is studied using the method of content analysis, and then categorised, analysed, and the conclusions are presented here. The shortcoming of the interviews of the Monument Board is that they do not have an inventory number and therefore can be referred to only by the names of the informants and municipalities they live in.

Discussion

Evidence of reused garments and accessories suggests that there are three main ways of reusing traditional Latvian garments and accessories: use of the garment in different context; destroying the garment in order to reuse its fabric; repurposing the use of the accessories.

There are two main types of peasant's clothing: everyday clothing for work and festive clothing for attending the church, proposing and engagements, weddings, christenings, and funerals. In the first half and middle of the 19th century when the traditional clothing was still in use, every

grownup peasant used to have one set of festive clothing (rarely two) and one or more sets of everyday clothing.

The analysed material suggests that it was a common practice to make special linen shirts to be worn for work. They were of much coarser fabric than those for festive clothing. Sometimes there were also skirts or trousers made from coarse fabric to be used for work. At the same time jackets, coats and hats were almost never made for work only for festive wear. The analysed material indicates that it was widely practiced to use worn-out festive clothing for everyday dress. There was much more demand for everyday clothing as it was used more often and it soon became damaged and useless due to hard and continued use. Therefore a person could have one set of festive clothing for a relatively long period and several sets of everyday clothing until they became worn out. The material shows that a garment of festive clothing could be first used for very important festive occasions, later it was worn on Sundays or going to the market and finally old festive garments were used for everyday wear and work until they were not wearable. A change of fashion could influence this process. The most dramatic changes in fashion took place in the sixties and seventies of the 19th century when the traditional clothing became unfashionable and was replaced by European town fashion (Karlson 2013: 17–20; Uļanovska 2017: 39–40).

The practice of using the outworn festive garments for everyday clothing was mentioned in the interviews: in Cibla municipality, 1926; Irēna Graznova, born in 1842, in Rundēni municipality, 1937; Antons Teicāns, 75 years old, in Mērdzene municipality, 1937; Agata Bļudņiks, 80 years old, in Briģi municipality, 1937; Ludvigs Strumps, 64 years old, and Zuzanna Rimže, 87 years old, in Pilda municipality, 1937.

Another way of using the festive clothing was that carefully worn festive dress (sometimes wedding clothing) and footwear was kept to become the funerary attire and thus was buried together with its wearer. This was confirmed by Sofija Līgnerskis, 80 years old, Silajāņi municipality, 1943; and Irēna Graznova, born in 1842, in Rundēni municipality, 1937. The interviewed people indicated that the festive dress was usually worn with great care, and this was mainly done due to poverty. Moreover they could not afford to keep newly-made wedding/funerary attire and had to wear it until it did not show signs of being worn out.

It can be concluded that using festive clothing in different context – as everyday wear or as funerary attire – completely extinguished these garments and they were not available for ethnographers who were later collecting items for museum collections.

The analysed material points out that destroying the garment in order to reuse its fabric was also a widespread practice. In this case it did not matter whether it was a festive garment or an everyday garment, as both could be used this way. The fabric of festive garments, however, was more frequently used for making other clothing as it was of better quality. These were most often

old fashioned garments that belonged to festive clothing and were not worn out yet: traditional woollen shawls and skirts. The interviews that mention re-sewing them into other garments (e.g. a fashionable dress) are by Viktora Vaspan, 60 years old, in Silajāņi municipality, 1943; and Veronika Skutel, in Vidsmuiža municipality, 1926. Stefania Ulanowska, Polish ethnographer, also writes that old fashioned traditional women's shawls with colorful embroidery have been long ago re-sewn into men's trousers or children's clothing and are no longer to be found in Viļāni municipality in 1891 (Uļanovska 2017: 41).

Outworn garments of traditional clothing could be destroyed in order to use their fabric for many purposes. The most common appears to be tearing old garments, especially coats, and making leg-wraps. This is mentioned by Adeļa Uzuleņš, 65 years old, in Nirza municipality, 1937; Agata Bļudniks, 80 years old, in Briģi municipality, 1937; Anna Strods, born in 1851, in Nautrēni municipality, 1937; and Zuzanna Rimže, 87, years old, in Pilda municipality, 1937. It is often said in the interviews that leg-wraps were commonly used for everyday wear, especially by men, however they were never made new. It can be argued that every man used many pairs of leg-wraps during his lifetime and therefore needed many old garments to satisfy the demand.

Another purpose of destroying garments was making nappies and swaddling-clothes for babies. As Sofija Līgnerskis, 80 years old, in Silajāņi municipality, 1943, puts it: a baby was first wrapped in an approximately 1 square meter of linen that was cut from an outworn man's shirt and then in a woollen piece that was cut from their mother's old skirt and tied with tablet-woven bands. One can imagine that most of the families had several children and each of them needed more than 10 nappies for a period of at least a year. This practice could form great demand for old traditional clothing.

Fig. 1. *A baby wrapped in old clothing and tied with a tablet-woven band. A reconstruction from a sketch by Auguste Siliņa, the Monument Board, 1943. Drawing by Laura Pīgozne.*

As a by-product of destroyed linen garments there were handkerchiefs made from the sleeves of shirts. Zuzanna Rimže, 87 years old, in Pilda municipality, 1937, confirms that. It can be presumed that these handkerchiefs were not used for decorative purposes but for blowing one's nose and were thrown out when they were worn out.

Last but not least the interviewed people told that outworn garments had been used as rags or sold to travelling Jewish merchants in order to be made into rags. This is mentioned by Irēna Gražnova, born in 1842, in Rundēni municipality, 1937; and Viktora Vaspan, 60 old, in Silajāņi municipality, 1943. Neighbour of the second informant, Marija Vaspāns, 64 years old, in Silajāņi municipality, 1943, also referred to woven rugs that were made of rags.

It can be concluded that only re-sewing garments could possibly lead to parts of the original garment to be preserved and potentially collected by the museums. All other ways of reusing them – as leg-wraps, nappies, handkerchiefs or rags – would eventually contribute to their ultimate disappearance.

There is more and more evidence gathered that woven sashes were used in women's clothing only while wrap-around skirts were worn. When women started to make skirts that were gathered around the waist and sewn to a waistband, sashes were no longer needed and therefore not worn. It seems that this could have happened in the 18th century or in the first half of the 19th century at the latest (Zariņa 1999: 40, 122; Petri 1809: 467–478). Tablet-woven sashes were, however, made and used in Latgale until the first half of the 20th century. They were still used by men to tie long coats and fur-coats (Bremze, Rozenberga, Ziņģīte 2003: 188, 195), but most importantly, they were repurposed and used in several other ways. It has been noted that sashes were used as gifts, for lowering coffin into the grave during funeral and as reins for horses (Bremze, Rozenberga, Ziņģīte 2003: 184).

Tens of interviews carried out by the Monument Board and the Latvian Folklore Archives indicate that sashes alone were rarely given as gifts. They could be given as offerings by the bride when she was walking around her new farm-stead for the first time and leaving “gifts” for the well, the bath-house, the gate, the cattle, etc. At the same time the newly married couple would receive gifts from their family and friends, and most women would present them with some handcrafted garments that were tied with a sash. The bride would give presents to the members of her husband's family, and these presents could also be tied with a sash. This means that sashes were used for decorative purposes as gift wraps. The interview with Sofija Līgnerskis, 80 years old, in Silajāņi municipality, 1943, confirms this. She also affirmed that women would wear a sash only if her skirt was too loose and otherwise would fall down. Anna Strods, born in 1851, in Nautrēni municipality, 1937, confirmed that women did not wear sashes except to tie a coat when working.

From other regions there are examples of blankets sewn together of many different sashes and they reflect the period of time when there were lots of sashes around but they were not used for clothing any more (Bremze, Rozenberga, Ziņģīte 2003: 81–82; Lietuvių liaudies menas 1957: fig. 238, 251). In Latgale there are no such blankets remaining, however, there is evidence that saddle-

pads were made of two sashes sewn together. This was noted by Zuzanna Rimže, 87 years old, in Pilda municipality, 1937.

Interview with Valentīna Usāne, born in 1933, conducted by Ieva Pīgozne in Galēni municipality in 2017 re-confirmed that woollen tablet-woven sashes were used for lowering coffin into the grave during the funeral, as well as they were used as upper parts of slippers with wooden soles. Interview with Veronika Meikulāne, born in 1939, in Galēni in 2017 also re-confirmed that babies were wrapped and then tied with tablet-woven sashes, and she showed a sash that had changed colours due to babies' urine. Interview with Anna Močāne, born in 1924 in Bērzpils, in 2017 reconfirmed that tablet-woven bands were used as reins for horses.

Fig. 2. *Valentīna Usāne demonstrating how sashes were used for upper parts of slippers.*
Photo by Ieva Pīgozne in Galēni, 2017.

Fig. 3. *A slipper with a wooden sole and an upper part made from sashes.*
A reconstruction by Ieva Pīgozne. Drawing by Laura Pīgozne.

It can be concluded that repurposing of sashes not only helped to preserve them, it also contributed to keeping the tradition of making them alive. This is why many sashes made their way to the museums and even century-old tablet-woven sashes can still be found in many homes in Latgale. Abundance of sashes probably also contributed to creating the false image of sashes being worn by women in the middle and second half of the 19th century.

Yet another part of clothing is footwear. Traditional Latgalian footwear is bast shoes (*vīzes*), cord shoes (*petērnes*), one-piece leather shoes (*pastalas*), slippers with a wooden sole and textile upper part (*klikatas*), and shoes and boots made of black, hard leather. The most commonly used were bast shoes, all leather footwear was considered to be expensive and prestigious. Bast shoes and one-piece leather shoes have been around for centuries and seem to be a very stable type of traditional footwear.

There are many interviews by the Monument Board that confirm wearing all types of traditional footwear, but the most valuable are those that provide information on how long a pair of traditional footwear could be worn until it was unusable. An interview from Stirniene municipality in 1926 affirms that bast shoes from osier bark could be worn for three days until they disintegrated, however, those made from linden bark could be worn for a week. If they were mended, they could last a little longer. Cord shoes could last for a month or two. When shoes could not be worn any longer they were burnt or thrown away. (Pigozne-Brinkmane 2008: 209) A pair of one piece leather shoes from Latgale at the National History Museum of Latvia (inventory number CVVM 5170) shows how they were mended several times, as there are two layers of patches on them. When the patches got holes, the shoes were thrown away. Interview with Irēna Graznova, born in 1842, in Rundēni municipality, 1937, suggests that the best footwear that people owned and wore for festive occasions was kept for their funerary attire and buried together with their wearer.

It can be argued that footwear was either worn out completely or kept for the funerary attire and very rarely any of it survived and was collected by the museums. Most of the bast shoes in museum collections are new or represented by just one shoe. Apparently they could be collected because there were so many of them made every year that people could afford to give a pair to the ethnographers. Other types of shoes could be collected if the museum worker was lucky to get outworn footwear before it was destroyed. This could explain why the museum collections have almost no other footwear but a few bast and cord shoes from Latgale in the 19th century.

Conclusions

Garments and accessories of traditional clothing in Latgale were used very thrifty in the 19th century. Due to shortage of resources most of the textile garments were used as long as it was possible. This often meant reusing their fabric for other wear or finally for rags. Only the festive garments that were made of better fabric could be used for making new garments or as lining and therefore could survive for a longer period. Evidence of the older garments therefore continued to exist alongside newer clothing, often hidden under the modern garments of town fashion. This represents a good example of how several layers of traditions coexisted simultaneously. Uncovering these different layers is one of the main tasks of the modern researchers (Alsupe 1983).

Many garments and footwear never made it to 1890s or 1920s and 30s when they could be collected by the museums. Interviews of the Monument Board mention that occasional garments were kept by the family as a memory of their older relatives. Very often these items were bought by the ethnographers and ended in the museum collections. This shows how little consequence there is of which items reached the museums. It would have been ideal, though not possible to pick an example of every typical garment that was made and worn in every decade of the 19th century and make sure it was represented in the museum collections.

This has two main consequences. One took place in the 1930 when the sets of Latgalian clothing were made based on what garments could be found in the National History Museum of Latvia. These sets included garments that were easy to collect, e.g. skirts from the last decade before the town fashion took over, more than 100 years old shawls that had survived as a memory of previous generations, bast shoes that were easiest to be found due to their quantity and above all sashes (Dzērvītis 1931; Karnups, Kivicka 1938). The other consequence is for the modern researchers who have to consider this complicated process of garments surviving and being collected by the museums and take all that into account when reviewing the sets of traditional Latgalian dress that were made in the 1930s. Today the research has to be done not only looking at the garments stored at the museums but also thoroughly studying the interviews by the Monument Board, Latvian Folklore Archives and every possible other source that is available. The time has come to consider “the whole picture” and review our perceptions of the traditional Latgalian dress in the 19th century.

Acknowledgement

Research presented here is done as one part of the research project “Development of Folk Dress in Latgale in the 19th Century”, project No. 1.1.1.2/VIAA/1/16/092. It is carried out under the activity 1.1.1.2. “Post-doctoral Research Aid” and financed by the European Regional Development Fund.

References

Unpublished sources:

Archives of the National History Museum of Latvia, inventory number code CVVM.
Archives of the Monument Board, stored at the National History Museum of Latvia.
Archives of Latvian Folklore, Collection of Traditions.

Published sources and literature:

Alsupe A. 1983. Kultūrvēsturisko slāņu problēma tautas lietišķajā mākslā. *Tautas mākslas vēstures un attīstības problēmas*. Rīga: LPSR ZA Vēstures institūts.
Bremze Z., Rozenberga V., Ziņģīte I. 1997. *Latviešu tautas tērpi = Latvian Folk Costumes*, Vol. 2. Rīga: Latvijas Vēstures muzejs.
Bremze Z., Rozenberga V., Ziņģīte I. 2003. *Latviešu tautas tērpi = Latvian Folk Costumes*, Vol. 3. Rīga: Latvijas Vēstures muzejs.
Dzērvītis A. 1931. *Latviešu tautas uzvalki*. Rīga: Latviešu dziesmu svētku biedrība.

- Jansone 2016. *Apģērba attīstība Zemgalē 19. gadsimtā*. Rīga: Latvijas Nacionālais kultūras centrs.
- Karlsona A. 2013. *Dziesmu svētki un tautiskā tērpa attīstība Latvijā 19. gadsimta beigās un 20. gadsimtā*. = *Song Festivals and the Development of National-style Dress in Latvia in the late 19th and 20th Centuries*. Rīga: Zinātne.
- Karnups A., Kivicka E. 1938. *Novadu tērpi*. Jelgava: Latvijas Lauksaimniecības kamera.
- Lietuvių liaudies menas*. 1957. Vilnius: Valstybinė grožinės literatūros leidykla.
- Petri J.C. 1809. *Neuestes Gemählde von Lief- und Ehistland, unter Katharina II und Alexander I: in historischer, statistischer, politischer und merkantilischer Ansicht*. Band II. Dycksche Buchhandlung.
- Pīgozne-Brinkmane I. 2008. Apavi kā senā goda apģērba daļa. *Letonica. Humanitāro zinātņu žurnāls*. Nr. 18, 202.–214. lpp.
- Slava M. 1973. Zemnieku apģērbs Latgalē (18. gs. beigās – 20. gs.). *Arheoloģija un etnogrāfija*
Nr. 10, 157.–188. lpp.
- Uļanovska S. 2017. *Poļu Infantijas latvieši. Etnogrāfisks tēlojums*.
Rēzekne: RTA. Zariņa A. *Apģērbs Latvijā 7.–17. gs*. Rīga: Zinātne.